

Effect of Corporate Social Ethical Responsibility on Customer Loyalty: A Survey of Telecommunication Firms in Uasin Gishu County, Kenya

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Abstract

Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) has been used by many companies to gain public confidence through providing essential commodities of some high value to a customer, particular in telecommunication industry where only one mobile operator has dominated the market share for the last one decade. The study objective was to determine the effect of CSR ethical responsibility on customer loyalty. Carroll model and Stakeholder theory were used to explaining the study. The study employed an explanatory research design. The study targeted all customers of telecommunication companies in Uasin Gishu County. Stratified sampling was used to group the population while the systematic sampling technique was used to obtain 400 customers. A structured questionnaire was used for data collection. The reliability of the questionnaire was checked using Cronbach Alpha test. Data was purely quantitative. Data collected were coded and analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. The study found that CSR initiatives positively impact on customer loyalty. The study found that ethical responsibilities positively affect customer loyalty. It was therefore affirmed that mobile firms providing telecommunication services with higher levels of ethical CSR initiatives are likely to enhance customer loyalty towards their products. It's therefore important for telecommunication firms to act as a good citizen in all matters beyond law and ethical rules. Telecommunication firms should engage in ethical CSR in order to create a positive attitude on their customers to enhance loyalty.

Keywords: *Corporate Social Responsibility, Ethical responsibility, Customer loyalty, and Telecommunication firms*

Introduction

CSR initiatives constitute a key element of corporate identity that can induce customers to identify for instance; customers through CSR can develop a sense of connection with the company. CSR initiatives can create benefits for companies by increasing consumers' identification with the corporation support for the company (Drumwright, and Bridgette, 2004). Customers are more likely to be satisfied with a firm's offerings to the community (Bhattacharya and Sen 2003). In addition, engaging in CSR may allow firms to understand their generalized customers better and thus improve their customer-specific knowledge (Sen and Bhattacharya 2001). Firms with satisfied customers tend to enjoy greater customer loyalty, positive word of mouth and customer's willingness to pay premium prices, all of which can increase a firm's market value as well as achieving higher levels of cash flows (Bolton and Drew, 1991; Szymanski and Henard, 2001; Homburg *et al.*, 2005).

In Kenya, Corporate social responsibility (CSR) promotes a vision of business accountability to a wide range of stakeholders, besides shareholders and investors. Key areas of concern are environmental protection and the wellbeing of employees, the community and civil society in general, both now and in the future. The concept of CSR is underpinned by the idea that corporations can no longer act as isolated economic entities operating in detachment from broader society. Traditional views about competitiveness, survival, and profitability are being swept away (Buchholtz, 2006). Some of the positive outcomes to the company as a result of CSR include; improved financial performance, lower operating costs enhanced brand image and reputation, increased sales and customer loyalty, greater productivity and quality, more ability to attract and retain employees, product safety and decreased liability. Benefits to the community and the general public include;

charitable contributions, employee volunteer programmes, corporate involvement in community education, employment and homelessness programmes (Feltus and Petit, 2009). Consequently, environmental benefits are; greater material recyclability, better product durability, and functionality, greater use of renewable resources, integration of environmental management tools into business plans, including life-cycle assessment and costing, environmental management standards, and eco-labeling.

Telecommunications services in Kenya have a long history. Presently, according to Communications Commission of Kenya (CCK) third Quarter Report for 2012/2013 released in April 2013, Kenya currently has around 30.4 million mobile phone subscribers, indicating a 77.2 percent penetration, according to a telecommunications sector report released by the country's industry regulator the CCK. The report, for the period between July and September 2012, also indicates a rise in the volume of mobile money transactions with KSh205 billion (US\$2.4 billion) deposited on the mobile money transfer services, up from the previous KSh192 billion (US\$2.2 billion) in the previous period, representing a 6.7 percent growth. According to CCK (2012), the mobile phone operator market in Kenya is comprised of Safaricom with the market share of 63.3%, Airtel with 15.3%, Essar with 8.7% and Orange at 10.6%.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Concept of Customer Loyalty

Customer loyalty refers to a deeply held commitment to make a repeat purchase or patronize a preferred product or service in the future despite there are situational influence and marketing efforts having the potential to cause switching behavior (Oliver, 1999). Customers are in a constant way of searching for some benefit from the company, hence CSR programs have positive effects on customers purchase (Maignan and Ferrell, 2004; Farooque *et al.*, 2009). Increased customer loyalty is one of the most common outcomes expected from relationship marketing efforts (Palmatier *et al.*, 2006). Most research has related customer loyalty with brand royalty but in this study, we shall look at service loyalty since we are dealing with the telecommunication sector which is a service industry.

Service loyalty refers the degree to which a customer exhibits repeat purchasing behaviour from a service provider, possesses a positive attitudinal disposition toward the provider, and considers using only this provider when a need for this service arises. (Caruana, 2002). In this study, loyalty is perceived as a continuous process of consuming and/or the buying of the products/services of a given firm over an unpredictable future period.

The link between CSR and Customer Loyalty

Researchers have shown CSR-related reactions to a company are determined not only by its actions in this domain but also by those of its stakeholder groups (for instance customers), which are typically beyond the company's control (Bhattacharya and Sen, 2003; Brown *et al.*, 2006; Pramanik *et al.*, 2007). CSR move beyond the often rarefied controlled empirical contexts to paint a more externally valid picture of the forces determining consumer reactions to CSR initiatives (Pramanik *et al.*, 2007). CSR actions are likely to be enacted. In other words, much as the competitive context impacts the marketing mix, a company, in formulating its CSR strategy, needs to understand how consumers perceive and react to its CSR actions not in isolation but in the context of different CSR actions, if any, taken by its competitors (Bhattacharya & Sen, 2004). Onlaor and Rotchanakitumnuai (2010) argue that organization should realize and invest in corporate social responsibility scheme in order to enhance their relationships with customers by initiating robust corporate strategy particularly in social concerns such as setting a reasonable price, improving their services, developing innovation, and implementing a privacy policy. Moreover, the organization should communicate CSR ways to the general public. Several marketing studies have reported that CSR behaviors can positively affect consumer attitudes

towards the firm and its offerings (Bhattacharya and Sen, 2003; Lichtenstein *et al.*, 2004; Luo and Bhattacharya, 2006).

Ethical Responsibilities and Customer Loyalty

Ethical responsibility is beyond legal requirements by considering in terms of standards, norms, and expectations which in turn reflect a concern for doing what is right, just, fair and to avoid harms to others (Shahin and Zairi, 2007). Vogel (2008) argued that consumers are more concerned about ethical products which are a niche market where all goods and services continue to be purchased on the basis of price, convenience, and quality. However, even in the niche market for ethical products, consumers may find it difficult to decide which firms to support (Cheers, 2011).

Ethical duties require that businesses abide by moral rules which define appropriate behaviours in society; they entail acting in a moral manner, doing what is right, just and fair; respecting people's moral rights, and avoiding harm or social injury as well as preventing harm caused by others. Ethical duties embrace those activities and practices that are expected or prohibited by society even though they are not codified into law (Carroll, 1991).

Williams (2006) argues that throughout time, corporations have often broken the rules of ethical conduct in business, which led to mistrust in their activity. A CSR approach may lead to an improvement of company's relation with interested groups, to greater transparency and to higher ethical standards; Carrigan and Attalla (2001) argue that although consumers may express a desire to support ethical companies and punish unethical firms, their actual purchase behaviour often remains unaffected by ethical concerns

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study adopted an explanatory research design. Explanatory research focuses on why questions and also causal relationships design. Answering the 'why' questions involves developing causal explanations. Causal explanations argue that phenomenon Y (customer loyalty) is affected by factor X (CSR Ethical initiative). Some causal explanations will be simple while others will be more complex (De Vaus, 2001). The population of the study comprised three major telecommunication firms in Uasin Gishu County namely; Safaricom, Airtel, and Orange. As at 15th January 2013, there were estimated 850,000 mobile subscribers in Uasin Gishu County comprising of 498,222 Safaricom subscribers, 207,517 Airtel subscribers and 141,600 Orange subscribers (CCK database, 2013). From the target population of 847,339, Taro Yamane (1973) sample size formula was used to calculate a sample size of 400 customers as shown below;

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2}$$

Where; n = Sample size, N = Population size and e = the error of Sampling

This study allowed the error of sampling of 0.05. Thus, the sample size will be as follows:

The study used a stratified sampling technique. Therefore, customers were stratified into three strata's where the sample size was distributed according to Neyman (1934) allocation formula. The purpose of the method is to maximize survey precision, given a fixed sample size. With Neyman allocation, the best sample size for stratum h would be:

$$n_h = \left(\frac{N_h}{N} \right) n$$

Where; n_h - The sample size for stratum h, n - Total sample size, N_h - The population size for stratum h, and N - The total population

Questionnaires were used to collect the relevant quantitative data, with crobach alpha being used to determine the reliability of the scales used. The data collected was analyzed using descriptive statistical techniques such as frequencies, mean, and standard deviation and presented using tables. The researcher also used inferential

statistics (t-test) and employed a Pearson correlation to show the relationships that exist between the variables. Multiple regressions analysis was also performed to show the causal effect.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Ethical Responsibilities

Study results in Table 1 revealed mobile services firms followed fundamental ethical principles (mean = 3.67). They were also shown to provide full and accurate product user information, to enhance user safety beyond legal requirements (mean = 3.66). Findings also indicated that mobile services firms use the information to specific markets and promote as a product advantage (mean 3.64) and ensure quality assurance criteria that are adhered to in production (mean = 3.54) and lastly true morality was first and foremost self-interested (mean = 3.41). Mobile services firms were rated to do better on ethical responsibilities (mean of 3.5042, the standard deviation of 0.64465, skewness -0.538 and kurtosis of 0.91).

Table 1 Ethical Responsibilities

	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness	Kurtosis
The firm follow fundamental ethical principles (honesty in product labeling)	3.67	1.032	-0.629	-0.012
The firm Provide full and accurate product use information, to enhance user safety beyond legal requirements	3.66	0.964	-0.518	-0.368
The firm target product use the information to specific markets (children, foreign speakers) and promote as a product advantage	3.64	0.978	-0.623	-0.002
The firm ensures quality assurance criteria that are adhered to in the production	3.54	1.015	-0.633	0.139
True morality is first and foremost self-interested	3.41	1.02	-0.529	-0.14
Ethical Responsibilities	3.5042	0.64465	-0.538	0.91

Survey data (2013)

Customer Loyalty

In Table 2 customer loyalty toward mobile service, firms were established. Results indicated that customers could not switch to another network because the one they were operating on was up to their standard (mean = 3.96). They were willing to keep on using the firm services/products (mean = 3.87) and preferred their service provider than any other firm (mean = 3.77). They also revealed that they could recommend the firm products/services to other people (mean = 3.72). In general, customers were loyal to their mobile services provider as evidence of mean, 3.837, standard deviation 0.66339, skewness -0.507 and kurtosis of 0.308.

Table 2 Customer Loyalty

	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness	Kurtosis
I Cannot Switch To Another Network because The One Am Operating In Is Up To My Standard.	3.96	1.162	-1.201	0.714
Am Willing To Keep On Using The Firm Services/Products	3.87	0.947	-0.9	0.796
I Prefer My Service Provider than any other Firm	3.77	0.996	-0.675	0.076
I Can Recommend the Firm Products/ Services to other People	3.72	1.041	-0.891	0.34
Customer	3.837	0.66339	-0.507	0.308

Survey data (2013)

Correlation Statistics

Pearson Correlations results showed that Ethical responsibilities were positively and significantly associated with customer loyalty as shown by $r = 0.650$, $\rho < 0.05$ implying that ethical responsibilities had 65% positive relationship with customer loyalty. Findings provided enough evidence to suggest that there was a linear relationship between ethical responsibilities and customer loyalty.

Table 3 Correlation Statistics of Independent and Dependent Variable

	Customer Loyalty	Ethical responsibilities
Customer loyalty	1	
Ethical Responsibilities	.650**	1

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).
Survey data (2013)

Multiple Regression Results to test the hypothesis

The study multiple regression model had a coefficient of determination (R^2) of about 0.622; this means that ethical responsibilities explain 62.2% variations of customer loyalty in mobile services firms. Durbin–Watson statistic is substantially less than 2, there is evidence of positive serial correlation, although positive serial correlation does not affect the consistency of the estimated regression coefficients, it does affect the ability to conduct valid statistical tests, as such it can be concluded that the significant statistics are valid. The study had F-value of 139.914 with a p value of 0.00 significant at 5% indicate that the overall regression model is significant.

Test of Hypotheses

The study hypothesis (H_0) of the study postulated that Ethical responsibilities have no significant effect on customer loyalty. The study findings showed that this hypothesis was rejected as illustrated by $\beta_4 = 0.236$, $\rho < 0.05$, thus, ethical responsibility has a significant positive effect on customer loyalty in mobile services firms. Hence, increasing ethical responsibilities' in mobile service firms will stimulate the customer to be loyalty to the firms' services.

Table 3 Multiple Regression Results

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients			Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta	T	Sig.	Tolerance	VIF
(Constant)	0.844	0.135		6.271	0.000		
Ethical Responsibilities	0.243	0.048	0.236	5.118	0.000	0.521	1.918
R Square		0.622					
Adjusted R Square		0.618					
F		139.914					
Sig.		.000					
Durbin-Watson		1.336					

a Dependent Variable: Customer loyalty

Survey data (2013)

Summary of the Findings

Ethical responsibility has a significant positive effect on customer loyalty in mobile services firms ($\beta_4 = 0.236$). This implies that mobile service firms with a high level of ethical responsibilities enhance their customer loyalty. This was echoed by Vogel (2008) consumers are more concerned about ethical products hence creating continuity of goods and services from the firm on the basis of price, convenience, and quality. However, even in the niche market for ethical products, consumers may find it difficult to decide which firms to support (Cheers, 2011). It is therefore suggested that CSR approach may lead to an improvement of the company's relation with interested groups, to greater transparency and to higher ethical standards. Carrigan and Attalla (2001) argue that although consumers may express a desire to support ethical companies and punish unethical firms, their actual purchase behaviour often remains unaffected by ethical concerns. Angelopoulos (2006) underlines that the benefits of promoting CSR are not limited to the external environment of the company (better reputation, expansion of the client base, penetration of new markets), since CSR initiatives may also have a significant impact on the internal environment (increase in employee productivity and loyalty, development of competitive advantage). Additionally, companies may become more effective in the recruitment and retention of talented employees, as people may have positive feelings when working for a socially responsible company (Cone *et al.*, 2003; Drumwright and Murphy, 2001).

Conclusions

The study CSR's impact on consumers' loyalty is in line with the research that generally suggests that the influence on companies' market performance is positive in terms of affecting customer loyalty and purchasing behavior. The study reconfirms this for the telecommunication industry. Findings provided enough evidence that CSR is more important as a direct factor of influence on customer loyalty. The results indicate that communication of CSR activities, highlighting the most important CSR domains, both at the point of sale and in general marketing communications is important to keep consumers informed about the companies' activities. Study reveals that while retailers engage highly in communicating their CSR activities, these CSR activities, however, in some cases are not perceived by the consumers. This research result indicates that there is a direct and positive relationship between CSR and customer loyalty, therefore, forming a basis for other studies.

Policy Recommendation

Customer perception about the firm quality products and services, reasonable price, innovation on technologies and fundamental ethical principles will have an impact on customer satisfaction which in turn leads to customer loyalty. Organisations should realize and invest in ethical corporate social responsibility scheme in order to enhance their relationships with customers by initiating robust corporate strategy, particularly in social concerns. Moreover, the organization should communicate CSR ways to the general public.

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